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Imprinting effectors in the mammalian nucleus.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We provide here a brief outline of the array of nuclear effectors that execute Xist-based epigenetic imprinting in the mammalian cell.

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Results

Type I: Direct imprinting effectors

DAZL
DAZAP
Dzip: DAZ interacting protein
ZIM
ZIC: zinc finger protein of the cerebellum

Type II: Early imprinting regulation

Zfp36l1
Zfp36l2
Zfp36

Type III: General imprinting effectors

Zfyve
Zmym
Zdhhc
Zc_h_
Zmynd
Zcchc
Zscan
Zkscan
Zswim
Zfand
Zc_hc_a
Zmiz

Specific Znf and Zfp family genes

Type IV: Early imprinting regulation (II)

Zfp
Zbtb
Zbtb7a/b
Bhlhe
Bhlhe40/41
Zxd(a/b/c)

Type V: Non-imprinting based Xist associated effectors

Lzts
Dpf

Type VI: Xist RNP-based imprinting effectors

Baz
KH-domain
KHDRBS
KHDC
QKI
KHNYN

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TDRKH
KHSRP

Type VII: Topologic regulation of Xist

FIRRE: functional intergenic repeating RNA element
Dxz4 locus effectors
DANT2: DXZ4 associated non-coding transcript 2
DANT3